

Evaluation of water and nutrients use efficiency in a cucumber-melon cascade hydroponic system

Nikolaos Katsoulas*, Ioannis Naounoulis, Sofia Faliagka, Efi Levizou

University of Thessaly, Dept. of Agriculture Crop Production and Rural Env., Fytokou Str, 38446, Volos, Greece

* Corresponding author. Email: email: nkatsoul@uth.gr

Abstract

Minimising water and fertiliser consumption is of high importance for the sustainability of greenhouse cultivation in the Mediterranean. Cascade soilless systems, have the ability to increase the water and nutrients use efficiency, while significantly reducing the water and nutrients leaching into the environment. In this study, a cascade cropping system in which the drainages from a hydroponic cucumber crop were recycled to irrigate a hydroponic melon crop was evaluated. The results showed that the recycled nutrient solution did not affect the yield of the melon plants compared to those irrigated with a standard nutrient solution. Additionally, the leaching of nitrates and phosphates into the environment was decreased by 75% and 86%, respectively. Finally, the implementation of the cascade system, increase by 22% the water use efficiency compared to the cucumber monoculture system.

Keywords: drainage management; water recirculation; fertilisers use efficiency; water productivity; greenhouse.

1. Introduction

The high productivity of greenhouse crops is related to high resource consumption. The soilless cultivations where they are growing in a substrate, are aver-irrigated (25-40%) in order to avoid salt accumulation in the rhizosphere. In closed hydroponic systems, the drained nutrient solution is collected and reused, maximising the water and nutrient use efficiency while significantly reducing the environmental impact of agriculture (Thomson et al., 2007; Massa et al., 2020). However, the use of low-quality irrigation water prevents the application of a totally closed hydroponic system (Katsoulas and Voogt, 2014). Consequently, after a certain number of recycles, it becomes necessary to remove the drainage nutrient solution to prevent the high concentration of toxic ions in the rhizosphere (Carmassi et al., 2005; Massa et al., 2010). As a result, many growers in the Mediterranean region act their systems as open hydroponic systems polluting the groundwater, due to the leaching of nitrate and phosphate ions.

A sustainable approach is the recycling and reusing of the drainage nutrient solution, to meet the needs of a secondary crop with higher salinity tolerance through a cascade hydroponic system. In these systems, the drainage of a primary (donor) crop, is collected and reused for the irrigation of a secondary (receiver) crop, which is more resistant to salinity (Karatsivou et al., 2023). While the drainage solution is reused, it becomes progressively more saline, but the concentration of nutrients such as nitrate and phosphate ions significantly decrease (Muñoz et al., 2010). A cascade hydroponic system is based on the idea of the circular economy, where according to the EU (EU 2008), resources remain within the system for the purpose of reuse and reducing waste in the environment. Additionally, a cascade hydroponic system is compatible and economically sustainable for lower-tech hydroponic installations, which are predominant in the Mediterranean region (Elvanidi et al., 2020).

Some preliminary studies were conducted on soil-grown cultivations such as in California's San Joaquin Valley. The system was developed to reuse high-conductivity drainage irrigation water on plants with moderate sensitivity to salinity as well as on halophytes (Grieve and Suarez, 1997; Shannon et al., 2000). However, there were difficulties concerning its technical application. In experiments conducted by Muñoz et al. (2010), the drainage solution from a hydroponic tomato crop was used to irrigate a soil-grown tomato crop. The adoption of this system resulted in a 21% reduction in the environmental footprint of the secondary crop.

More recent studies, focuses on the strategy of reusing drainage solution in crops with progressively increasing salt tolerance and lower input requirements. One of the main issues is finding alternative cultivated species that remain productive under high salinity conditions (Grieve and Suarez, 1997). Additionally, the heterogeneity of crops within a system may necessitate greater technical specialisation in system management (Massa et al., 2020). Moreover, the ratio of the cultivated area of primary to secondary crops

required by each system is one of the key factors in selecting the appropriate "pairing" of species to be cultivated. The economic performance of the secondary crop can significantly limit the income of producers, as the cultivation of lower input-demanding crops often results in reduced yield per unit area. Therefore, further investigation is necessary to find suitable combinations and develop profitable cascade cropping systems.

Aim of this study was to evaluate the sustainability and the performance of a cascade hydroponic cultivation system, in which the drainages from a cucumber (donor) crop were collected and reused to meet the needs of a melon (receiver) crop. The findings of this research are expected to significantly contribute to the advancement of cascade cultivation systems, while simultaneously providing solutions for minimising water and fertiliser requirements in the agricultural sector.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Experimental Design

The experiment was conducted at the greenhouse park of the Laboratory of Agricultural Constructions and Environmental Control, of the Department of Agriculture Crop Production and Rural Environment at the University of Thessaly, in the area of Velestino (39° 22', 22° 44', 85 m).

The transplanting of the primary cucumber crop (*Cucumis sativus* cv. Columbia) took place on March 15, 2023, in two compartments of a gothic-type greenhouse with a polyethylene roof covering, each with a total area of 240 m². Each compartment consisted of 6 hydroponic channels, each 20 m in length. The roof of each compartment was equipped with a continuous opening for ventilation, and the cooling system consisted of a wet pad and a fan. The plants were received in rock wool cubes (Grodan, Netherlands) (7.5x7.5 cm) and placed in perlite bags (Hydroperl, NORDIA AGRO, Athens, Greece), with a total volume of 33 L. The planting density was 1.08 plants m⁻². The primary crop was fertigated with a nutrient solution for cucumber crops in open systems (Savvas, 2011). The climate was automated controlled via a climate computer (Sercom, Netherlands). The irrigation system was activated through an automation system (Argos Electronics, Athens, Greece).

The secondary crop was developed in a modified simple arched greenhouse, with a total ground area of 160 m² and a cultivated area of 86 m². Eight hydroponic channels, each 12.5 m long, were installed inside the greenhouse. A fog system (Air Petri, Lucca, Italy) was used for greenhouse cooling, while climate and irrigation were automatically controlled (Argos Electronics, Athens, Greece). Transplanting took place on April 10, 2023, and the cultivation period lasted a total of 101 days. The melon seedlings (*Cucumis melo* cv. Masada) were received in rock wool cubes (Grodan, Netherlands) (7.5x7.5 cm) and placed in perlite bags of 33 L (Geoflor, Athens). The planting density was set at 2.25 plants m⁻². The experimental design included two treatments: the "control" treatment, where the melon crop was irrigated with a standard hydroponic solution for melon crops in open systems according to Savvas (2011), and the "cascade" treatment, where the melon plants were irrigated with 100% drainage nutrient solution from the cucumber crop, after pH adjustment.

To evaluate the system's performance, a series of measurements were conducted concerning the total water uptake, nitrogen leaching, and water use efficiency. These measurements were carried out on a weekly basis, allowing for monitoring the system's progress.

2.2. Statistical Analysis

The comparison of mean values was performed using One Way ANOVA at a 95% confidence level ($p \leq 0.05$) with the statistical package SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences, IBM, Armonk, NY, USA). Additionally, the Least Significant Difference (LSD) method was used at a 5% significance level.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Water Consumption

A necessary condition for the proper design and implementation of a cascade cropping system is the proper ratio of cultivated area in order for the volume of the drainage nutrient solution from the primary crop to meet the water consumption needs of the secondary crop.

The total volume of the irrigation and drainage nutrient solution in the primary crop was 331.5 L m⁻² and 136.2 L m⁻², respectively. For the irrigation of the secondary crop cascade during the cultivation period, a total of 385.8 L m⁻² of the drainage solution of the primary crop was used, with a leaching fraction of 24%. The nutrient solution absorption in the cascade treatment did not differ from that in the control. According to the aforementioned values, the drainages from 1 m² of the primary cucumber crop were sufficient to meet the irrigation needs of 0.35 m² of the secondary melon crop. The ratio of cultivated area between the primary and secondary crops was, therefore, 3:1. More specifically, 1 m² of the cascade system studied was composed of 0.74 m² of the primary crop and 0.26 m² of the secondary crop. Additionally, the drainage nutrient solution that was ultimately discharged into the environment amounted to 9.6% of the initial irrigation solution volume of the primary crop, contrary to the 40% of the single cucumber crop (Table 1). Few studies have evaluated the ratio of the cultivated area between primary and secondary crops. García-Caparrós et al. (2018), reported a 1:4 ratio in a rosemary crop when irrigated with 100% drainage from a hydroponic melon crop. Incrocci et al. (2003) used the discharged solution from a semi-closed tomato cultivation system to irrigate a more salt-tolerant tomato crop. Their conclusions indicated that the discharged solution was sufficient to meet 50% of the secondary crop's water needs. However, contrary to the present study, Neocleous and Savvas (2016), in a hydroponic melon cultivation, observed that the crop consumed significantly less water when a slight increase in EC was recorded.

Table 1. Cumulative nutrient solution irrigation and drainage (L m⁻²) during the cultivation period

	Irrigation	Drainage
Primary Crop (cucumber)	331.5	136.2
Secondary crop control (melon)	401.7	109.9
Secondary crop cascade (melon)	385.8	90.2
Cascade system (cucumber+melon)	245.4	23.6

3.2. Water Use Efficiency

Water use efficiency (WUE) was calculated as the total fruit production (kg m⁻²) in relation to the total water consumption (m³ m⁻²). The results indicated a significant increase of the WUE when the cascade system was implemented. More specifically, the application of the cascade system increased the WUE by 22.1 and 131.8% compared to the cucumber and melon monoculture system, respectively (Table 2).

Similar results were also presented by Muñoz et al. (2017) where the reuse of drainages from a soilless tomato crop did not affect the WUE of a soil-based tomato crop. In case the cascade cropping system is considered as a single system and the drainage solution used for the irrigation of the secondary crop is not considered as a separate input to the system, then the WUE of the secondary crop increases significantly (Elvanidi et al., 2020).

Table 2. Water use efficiency (kg m⁻³) (± S.E.) of the primary, secondary crop control, secondary crop cascade, and cascade system. Different letters indicate the statistically significant differences (p<0.05)

	WUE
Primary Crop (cucumber)	46.7±1.5 ^b
Secondary crop control (melon)	24.6±1.4 ^c
Secondary crop cascade (melon)	26.4±3.2 ^c
Cascade system (cucumber+melon)	57.1±1.3 ^a

3.3. Total nitrate and phosphate leaching into the environment

The total leaching of N and P into the environment throughout the cultivation period, for both the primary and secondary crops as well as the combined cascade cropping system, are shown in Table 3. The total nitrate

drainage from the control and the cascade melon treatment presented similar results. The higher values recorded in the control treatment were a result of the higher drainage volume. Considering the two crops as a combined system, a significant reduction in nitrate leaching into the environment was observed. Specifically, from 1 m² of the primary crop resulted in an 70% reduction in nitrate ion leaching into the environment compared to the amount that would have been released without the implementation of the cascade cropping system. A significant reduction was also observed in the total phosphate discharge. As shown in Table 3, the total phosphate leaching from the cascade treatment was 50% lower than that of the control. Notably, the reduction was even more significant with the cascade cropping system where phosphate leaching from 1 m² of the primary crop decreased by 80%. This system effectively absorbs significant amounts of key macronutrients responsible for groundwater pollution.

Table 3. Mean total nitrogen and phosphorus leaching (g m⁻²) (±S.E.) of the primary, secondary crop control, secondary crop cascade, and cascade system. Different letters indicate the statistically significant differences (p<0.05)

	Nitrogen leaching	Phosphorus leaching
Primary Crop (cucumber)	18.4±0.1 ^c	2.8±0.1 ^c
Secondary crop control (melon)	22.4±1.6 ^a	4.0±0.2 ^a
Secondary crop cascade (melon)	20.9±0.2 ^b	2.1±0.1 ^b
Cascade system (cucumber+melon)	5.44±0.1 ^d	0.6±0.1 ^d

The results of related studies conclude that the implementation of a cascade cropping system significantly reduces environmental impacts (Incorci et al., 2003; Muñoz et al., 2010; García-Caparrós et al., 2015; Elvanidi et al., 2020). García-Caparrós et al. (2018) emphasised that the application of a cascade cropping system resulted in water savings and nitrate removal, which is a significant advantage in arid and semi-arid regions, such as the Mediterranean.

3.4. Crop Yield

To assess of the productivity of a cascade cropping system, the evaluation of the yield of the secondary crop in considered necessary. In this study, the fruit harvest for both treatments began on the 71st day of the experiment and lasted for 32 days. As shown in Figure 4, the total cumulative yield did not differ between treatments. Specifically, at the last harvest, the total yield for both treatments was 9.8 kg m⁻² and 9.7 kg m⁻² for the control and the cascade treatment, respectively.

Figure 4. Cumulative yield (±S.E.) of the secondary crop (kg m⁻²). Empty dots indicate the control treatment; filled dots indicate cascade treatment.

Melon is characterised as a moderately sensitive to salinity crop, as opposed to cucumber crops that are in general more susceptible to salinity (Savvas, 2011). Bar-Yosef (2008) reported that an increase in EC in the root zone from 2.1 to 4.6 dS m⁻¹ in a closed hydroponic melon cultivation system reduced yield by 19.6%. The adverse effects of high EC in the root environment of melon plants can be mitigated by using grafting techniques (Colla et al., 2006). Indeed, the results of this study are consistent with those of Romero et al. (1997), where grafted melon plants did not show a reduction in yield even when exposed to an EC of 4.6 dS m⁻¹. Similar studies have recorded a decrease in the yield of the secondary crop with the application of a coupled system (García-Caparrós et al., 2018, Elvanidi et al., 2020, Avdouli et al., 2021, Karatsivou et al.,

2023). In experiments where the secondary crop was grown in soil (Muñoz et al., 2010; Muñoz et al., 2017), there was no significant decrease in yield, making it a sustainable solution for waste management.

4. Conclusions

The combination of primary and secondary crops is the main factor for the sustainability of a cascade cropping system. The composition of the drainage solution from the primary crop should meet the nutrient needs of the secondary crop. The reusing of cucumber drainages to meet the needs of a soilless melon crop proves to be a sustainable combination. The reuse of the drainage solution did not negatively affect the yield of the melon crop. At the same time, significant amounts of major pollutants were removed, making the final discharged solution safer for the environment. The simplicity of implementing the system and the lack of need for specialised knowledge for its application make it an ideal solution for addressing the environmental impacts caused by greenhouse production.

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